

Purification of ACVR2, Alk3 (BMPR1A) and Alk6 (BMPR1B).

Rationale:

ACVR2A, Alk3 and Alk6 are structurally similar to Alk2 and thus a crystal structure of any of these with the M4KPharma compounds of interest would be of use for future drug development.

Aim:

Purify ACVR2, Alk3 and Alk6 for use in crystallography studies.

Proteins to be purified:

ACVR2A-c046

SMPLQLLEVKARGRFGCVWKAQLLNEYVAVKIFPIQDKQSWQNEYEVYSLPGMKHENILQFIGAEKRGTSVDVDL
WLITAFHEKGSLSDFLKANVVSWNELCHIAETMARGLAYLHEDIPGLKDGHKPAISHRDIKSKNVLLKNNLTACIADF
GLALKFEAGKSAGDTHGQVGTRRYMAPEVLEGAINFQRDAFLRIDMYAMGLVLWELASRCTAADGPVDEYMLPF
EEEIGQHPSLEDMQEVVVHKKKRPVLRDYWQKHAGMAMLCETIEECWDHDAEARLSAGCVGERITQMQLRTNI

BMPR1AA-c018

SMAFIPVGESLKDLDIQSQSSGSGSGLPLLQRTIAKQIQMVRQVGKGRYGEVWMGKWRGEKVAVKVFFTTEEAS
WFRETEIYQTVLMRHENILGFIAADIKGTGSWTQLYLITDYHENGSLYDFLKCATLDTRALLKLAYSAAACGLCHLHTEI
YGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILKNGSCCIADLGLAVKFNSDTNEVDVPLNTRVGTKRYMAPEVLDES LNKNHFQPYI
MADIYSFGLIIEWEMARRCITGGIVEEYQLPYNMMVPSDPSYEDMREVVCVKRLRPVSNRWNSDECLRAVLKLMSE
CWAHNPASRLTALRIKKTAKMSESQDVKI

BMPR1BA-c017

SMTYIPPGESLRDLIEQSQSSGSGSGLPLLQRTIAKQIQMVKQIGKGRYGEVWMGKWRGEKVAVKVFFTTEEAS
WFRETEIYQTVLMRHENILGFIAADIKGTGSWTQLYLITDYHENGSLYDYLKSTTLDAKSMKLAYS SVSGLCHLHTEI
FSTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGTCCCIADLGLAVKFISDTNEVDIPPNTRVGTKRYMPPEVLDES LN RNHFQSYIM
ADMYSFGLILWEVARRCVSGGIVEEYQLPYHDLVPSDPSYEDMREIVCIKLRPSFPNRWSSDECLRQMGLMTEC
WAHNPASRLTALRVKKTAKMSESQDIKL

Expression:

All proteins were expressed in Sf9 insect cells by Shubash at 27°C for 72 hours in glass shaker flasks.

Purification:

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice.

- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (approx 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate lysate with 2ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

SDS-PAGE gel of Nickle purification of ACVR2, BMPR1A (Alk3), BMPR1B (Alk6) showing flow through, washes 1 and 2 and four elution fractions. The red box indicates samples taken on for additional purification.

- Pool elution fractions E1 - E4(3)
- Add Tev protease to fractions which contain protein (Wash 2, E1, E4₁)
- Concentrate down boxed samples to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.
- Use mass spec to confirm protein has cleaved.

SDS-PAGE gel of gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a size exclusions GF75 column. The red box indicates the samples taken forward for use.

ACVR2 Nickle rebind:

- Incomplete cleavage of ACVR2 was observed.
- Ni rebind to separate out cleaved and uncleaved protein.
- Pour relevant pooled fractions over 1ml pre-equilibrated nickle resin and collect flow through.
- Pass flow through over beads a further two times and collect flow through.
- Wash with 2 x 7ml binding buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Elute with 2 x 7ml elution buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Collect fractions and run gel of all fractions.
- Confirm mass by mass spec. Elution fractions contain single species of protein.
- Pool Elution fractions for use in crystallography.

(Left) SDS-PAGE gel of the ni-rebind of ACVR2 showing initial sample, the flow through, two wash fractions and two elution fractions. Red box indicates samples taken forward for crystallisation. (Right) Mass spec confirms mass with N-methionine removal and subsequent acetylation as likely cause of mass difference. Only one species observed suggesting no mixed cleaved/uncleaved product present.

Crystallography:

- Concentrate protein down to 12mg/ml
- Add compound at 0.5mM concentration. (Compounds in this case M4K2009, M4K3003 and M4K3007)
- Spin for 15 minutes at 14,000 rpm to remove precipitant
- Set up crystal plates using coarse screens as follows:
Protein concentration 12 mg/ml Ligand concentration at 0.5mM
Single sized drops (150nl), 3 drop ratio (1:2, 2:2, 2:1)

Bar code	Screen	Additives	Comments:
CI071500	JCSG7	M4K2009	20C
CI071501	LFS6	M4K2009	20C
CI071502	HCS3	M4K2009	4C
CI071503	HIN3	M4K2009	4C
CI071510	JCSG7	M4K3007	20C
CI071511	LFS6	M4K3007	20C
CI071512	HCS3	M4K3007	4C
CI071513	HIN3	M4K3007	4C
CI071520	JCSG7	M4K3003	20C
CI071521	LFS6	M4K3003	20C
CI071522	HCS3	M4K3003	4C
CI071523	HIN3	M4K3003	4C